

The Effect of Religious Affiliation and Gender on Spiritual Intelligence: A Comparative Study

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In this research article, a comparative and regression analysis was conducted to examine the effects of religious affiliation, gender, and their interaction on Spiritual Intelligence. For this purpose, King's (2008) Spiritual Intelligence Self-Report Inventory (SISRI-24) was administered to male and female participants belonging to Hindu and Muslim groups. The significance of differences in overall Spiritual Intelligence and its four dimensions across the four groups was assessed using responses from a total sample of 400 participants (100 per group). The findings indicate significant differences between the religious groups in overall Spiritual Intelligence and all four of its dimensions. Among the gender groups, significant differences were observed on all dimensions except Critical Existential Thinking. The interaction effect of religion and gender on this scale was not significant for any dimension. The regression results of this study further show that religion has a significant predictive effect on Spiritual Intelligence ($R = 0.225$, $R^2 = 0.051$, Adjusted $R^2 = 0.048$, $F(1, 397) = 21.19$, $p < .01$). However, neither gender nor the interaction term (religion \times gender) was a significant predictor in the regression model. Based on these results and hypothesis testing (Null Hypothesis), religious affiliation emerges as a significant predictor of Spiritual Intelligence, while gender also shows a meaningful effect. The non-significant interaction effect (Gender & Religion) on this scale indicates that the response patterns of males and females across both religious groups are not divergent but generally follow the same direction.

Keywords: Spiritual intelligence, critical thinking, personal meaning, transcendental awareness, conscious state

The term "Spiritual Intelligence" was first introduced by Zohar (1997) in her book 'Spiritual Intelligence: The Ultimate Intelligence'. Literally, the term signifies wind or breath-the vital life force flowing within us, the inner capacity that keeps us alive and makes us human. However, the conceptual roots of spiritual intelligence can be traced to Gardner's (1987) theory of multiple intelligences, particularly his description of Existential Intelligence. While explaining this construct, Gardner (1987) stated that 'existential intelligence is the capacity to deal with deep questions related to human existence.' Emmons (1999, 2000a) argued that spirituality can be viewed as a form of intelligence because it predicts functioning and offers capabilities that enable people to solve problems and attain valuable goals. In other words, spirituality is based on abilities that produce valuable outcomes. He draws on Gardner's definition of intelligence

and argues that spirituality can be viewed as a form of intelligence because it predicts functioning and adaptation and offers capabilities that enable people to solve problems and attain goals. Spiritual intelligence places a greater emphasis on abilities that draw on such spiritual themes to predict functioning and adaptation and to produce valuable products or outcomes (Emmons, 1999, 2000a, 2000b). Over time, this intelligence type played a significant role in shaping the importance and conceptual structure of spiritual intelligence. Further refining his ideas, Gardner (1999) highlighted the relevance of spiritual intelligence, noting that "*Spiritual intelligence may be an intelligence concerned with ultimate issues, enabling individuals to contemplate profound questions such as life, death, and existence.*" According to Zohar and Marshall (2000), defined SI as "*The intelligence with which we address and solve problems of meaning and value, the intelligence with which we can place our actions and our lives in a wider, richer, meaning-giving context*". In other words, it is the ability to connect actions with deeper values, understand the meaning and purpose of life, and make appropriate moral decisions in complex situations. They emphasised spiritual intelligence as the ability to transcend the Ego, connect with a higher purpose, and recognise oneself as an integral part of the universe. Sisk (2002) explained spiritual intelligence as the holistic resolution of value-based life problems through the use of multisensory approaches. According to Sisk (2002), "*spiritual intelligence involves using multisensory perspectives to resolve issues related to meaning and value, and to view life as an interconnected whole.*" Nasel (2004) suggests that spiritual intelligence is associated with deriving personal meaning from existential issues and developing deep insights about life and death. "*Spiritual intelligence refers to*

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apply and interpret spiritual experience for meaning-making and emotional regulation. Emmons (2000a) proposed five components for Spiritual intelligence: (a) the ability to utilize spiritual resources to solve problems, (b) the ability to enter heightened states of consciousness, (c) the ability to invest everyday activities and relationships with a sense of the sacred, (d) the capacity for transcendence of the physical and material, and (e) the capacity to be virtuous.

Similarly, King (2008) explained that “*spiritual intelligence is a set of mental capacities which contribute to the awareness, integration, and adaptive application of the non-material and transcendent aspects of the one's existence.*” Based on this refined definition, King identified measurable attributes of spiritual intelligence and classified them into four major components (Dimensions), for which he developed the SISRI-24 (Spiritual Intelligence Self-Report Inventory):

Critical Existential Thinking (CET): Measures an individual's ability to engage in deep reflection on life, death, and purpose and existence based on 7 items of SISRI-24.

Personal Meaning Production (PMP): Assesses how individuals derive meaning and purpose in their lives.

Transcendental Awareness (TA): Measures awareness of a higher power or reality beyond the self or sensory perception.

Conscious State Expansion (CSE): Assesses the experience of deep spiritual understanding beyond ordinary consciousness.

Review of Literature

A study conducted by Nasruddin et al. (2011) at the University of Malaya examined the differences in spiritual intelligence among students enrolled in professional and non-professional academic programs. Both male and female students from these streams were included as participants, and the SISRI-24 developed by King (2008) was used to measure their spiritual intelligence. The major findings of this study were as follows:

- Neither the main effect of gender nor the interaction effect of gender \times course was found to be significant.
- A significant difference was found between students of professional and non-professional programs in terms of spiritual intelligence.
- Students enrolled in professional courses exhibited higher levels of spirituality.

Objectives of the Study

- To measure and comparatively study the spiritual intelligence of male and female participants belonging to Hindu and Muslim religious groups.
- To highlight the interactive role of religion, gender, and the religion*gender interaction on spiritual intelligence.

Hypotheses of the Study

- *H01*: There will be no significant difference in the level of spiritual intelligence (SI) between male and female students.
- *H02*: There will be no significant difference in the level of spiritual intelligence (SI) between Hindu and Muslim students.
- *H03*: The interactive effect of religion and gender on spiritual intelligence will not be significant.

Method

In this research study, a 2 \times 2 factorial design was employed to determine

the significance of differences between religious and gender groups. For the religious factor, Hindu and Muslim groups were selected, and for the gender factor, male and female groups were selected. In this way, the differences among all four groups were examined.

Participants

A total of 400 Samples was selected using a purposive sampling technique. The study includes 100 participants, each from four groups: Muslim females, Muslim males, Hindu females, and Hindu males. All participants are undergraduate and postgraduate students from various colleges in Bihar.

Measure

For this study, the Self-report Inventory developed by King (2008) was used. It measures four dimensions of spiritual intelligence: CET (7 Items), PMP (5 Items), TA (7 Items) and CSE (5 Items). Responses are recorded on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 0 - 4.

Statistical Analysis

In this research study, the significance of differences among various groups was determined. For this purpose, the significance of differences was assessed using statistical analyses such as Mean, Standard Deviation, and Analysis of Variance. In order to examine the predictive effect of religious affiliation and gender, regression analysis was conducted.

Procedure

Both offline and online (Through Google Form) modes were used to collect data. The questionnaire for this scale, along with general information (like gender, religion, university name, marital & educational status) about the participants, was distributed to the respondents, and their responses were collected.

Table 1

Demographic Details of Participant's

University Affiliation	N
Vks University Ara	146
Bihar engineering university	52
Magadh University	47
Purnia University	46
Patliputra University	42
Patna University	34
Brab University	33
Educational Status (Enrolled)	N
Graduation	276
Post Graduation	124
Religion	N
Hindu	200
Muslim	200
Gender	N
Male	200
Female	200
Marital Status	N
Married Male	23
Unmarried Male	177
Total	200
Married Female	59
Unmarried Female	141
Total	200

Graph 1

The demographic characteristics of the sample are presented in the table and graph above. It provides numerical information on students enrolled in colleges affiliated with various universities in Bihar, categorized by their educational status, religious group, gender (male & female), and marital status.

Results

Table 2

Comparative Result on Spiritual Intelligence (SISRI-24)

Group	Hindu	Muslim	Total	F-ratio
Female	65.16,	57.07,	61.43,	Gender
Mean, (SD)	(13.13)	(14.24)	(14.17)	- 4.19*
Male Mean,	61.38,	55.61,	58.50,	Religion
(SD)	(14.34)	(15.46)	(15.14)	- 21.32**
Total Mean,	63.27,	56.66,	59.97,	Religion × Gender
(SD)	(13.84)	(14.85)	(14.72)	- 0.35

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$

Graph 2

Table 2 and Graph 2 present the numerical values of mean, SD and analysis of variance (ANOVA) to examine differences in Spiritual Intelligence (SI) across religious groups (Hindu & Muslim) and gender groups (Male & Female). The results revealed a statistically significant difference between the Hindu and Muslim participants at the .01 level, $F(1, 396) = 21.32, p < .01$. Specifically, the Hindu group of participants reported a higher level of Spiritual Intelligence (Mean = 63.27, $SD = 13.84$) compared to the Muslim group of participants (Mean = 56.66, $SD = 14.85$).

A significant gender difference also observed in the overall

Spiritual Intelligence score, $F(1, 396) = 4.19, p < .05$, indicating that females (Mean = 61.43, $SD = 14.17$) scored higher than males (Mean = 58.50, $SD = 15.14$). However, the interaction effect between religious group (Hindu & Muslim) and gender (Male & Female) was not statistically significant, suggesting that the influence of religion and gender on Spiritual Intelligence operates independently.

Table 3

Mean, SD and F ratio on the Measures of Critical Existential Thinking

Group	Hindu	Muslim	Total	F-ratio
Female	19.11,	16.42,	17.77,	Gender
Mean, (SD)	(4.14)	(4.82)	(4.68)	- 1.48
Male Mean,	17.97,	16.41,	17.20,	Religion
(SD)	(4.63)	(5.09)	(4.91)	- 20.53**
Total Mean,	18.54,	16.42,	17.48,	Religion × Gender
(SD)	(4.42)	(4.94)	(4.80)	- 1.48

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$

Graph 3

Table 3 and Graph 3 present the numerical values, mean, standard deviation, and the significance of differences among various religious and gender groups, as determined by analysis of variance (ANOVA). A significant difference was found between the religious groups ($F(1,396) = 20.53, p < .01$). This indicates that the Hindu group (Mean = 18.54, $SD = 4.42$) has a higher level of Critical Existential Thinking compared to the Muslim group (Mean = 16.42, $SD = 4.94$). On this dimension, neither the difference between gender groups (male & female) nor the interaction effect of religion and gender was significant.

Table 4

Mean, SD and F ratio on the Measures of Personal Meaning Production (PMP)

Group	Hindu	Muslim	Total	F-ratio
Female	14.51,	13.24,	13.88,	Gender
Mean, (SD)	(3.04)	(3.38)	(3.27)	- 4.03*
Male Mean,	13.98,	12.44,	13.21,	Religion
(SD)	(3.23)	(3.57)	(3.48)	- 18.00**
Total Mean,	14.25,	12.84,	14.54,	Religion × Gender
(SD)	(3.14)	(3.49)	(3.39)	- 0.17

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$

Table 4.1*Descriptive Result on Personal Meaning Production (PMP)*

Descriptive Result	Group							
	Hindu F.	Hindu M.	Muslim F.	Muslim M.	M.	F.	Hindu	Muslim
Mean	14.51	13.98	13.24	12.44	13.21	13.88	14.25	12.84
Median	15	14	13.50	13	14	14	15	13
Mode	13	17	14	14	14	13	17	14
SD	3.04	3.23	3.38	3.57	3.48	3.27	3.14	3.49
Sample Variance	9.22	10.42	11.44	12.77	12.14	10.68	9.84	12.21
Standard Error	0.30	0.32	0.34	0.36	0.25	0.23	0.22	0.25

Note. M. = Male, F. = Female

Table 4 and 4.1 presents a comparative analysis of the Spiritual Intelligence dimension related to the ability of Personal Meaning Production, using means, median, mode, standard deviations, and analysis of variance (ANOVA). A significant difference was found between the religious groups (Hindus & Muslims) [$F(1, 396) = 18.00, p < .01$]. This indicates that the Hindu group (Mean = 14.25, $SD = 3.14$) has a higher level of Personal Meaning Production ability than the Muslim group

(Mean = 12.84, $SD = 3.49$).

On this dimension (PMP), a significant difference was found between gender groups (male and female) [$F(1,396) = 4.03, p < .05$], while the interaction effect of religion and gender was not significant. This implies that the response patterns of males and females from both religious groups (Hindu & Muslim) do not differ in opposite directions; instead, they follow a similar and consistent direction.

Table 5*Mean, SD and F ratio on the Measures of Transcendental Awareness (TA)*

Group	Hindu	Muslim	Total	F-ratio
Female Mean, (SD)	18.49, (3.85)	15.86, (4.38)	17.18, (4.32)	Gender- 5.18*
Male Mean, (SD)	17.24, (4.15)	15.19, (4.46)	16.22, (4.42)	Religion- 30.78**
Total Mean, (SD)	17.87, (4.04)	15.53, (4.42)	16.70, (4.39)	Religion × Gender - 0.47

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$

Table 5.1

Descriptive Result/Group	Muslim	Hindu	Male	Female
Mean	15.53	17.87	16.22	17.18
Standard Error	0.31	0.29	0.31	0.31
Median	15.00	18.00	15.00	17.00
Mode	11.00	21.00	14.00	16.00
Standard Deviation	4.42	4.04	4.42	4.32
Sample Variance	19.56	16.35	19.53	18.67

Table 5 and 5.1 presents the statistical analysis (Descriptive & ANOVA) conducted to determine the significance of differences

between various groups (Religious & Gender). A significant difference was found between the religious groups (Hindu & Muslim) ($F(1,396) = 30.78, p < .01$). This indicates that the Hindu group (Mean = 17.87, $SD = 4.04$) has a higher level of Transcendental Awareness compared to the Muslim group (Mean = 15.53, $SD = 4.42$).

A significant difference was also observed between the gender groups ($F(1,396) = 5.18, p < .05$). This suggests that the female group (Mean = 17.18, $SD = 4.32$) shown higher Transcendental Awareness than the male group (Mean = 16.22, $SD = 4.42$).

The interaction effect of the two-factor design (Religion × Gender) on this dimension was not found to be significant.

Table 6*Mean, SD and F ratio on the Measures of Conscious State Expansion (CSE)*

Group	Hindu	Muslim	Total	F-ratio
Female Mean, (SD)	13.05, (3.51)	12.18, (2.85)	12.62, (4.32)	Gender- 4.85*
Male Mean, (SD)	12.19, (3.56)	11.57, (3.38)	11.88, (3.48)	Religion- 4.98*
Total Mean, (SD)	12.62, (3.55)	11.88, (3.13)	12.25, (3.37)	Religion × Gender 0.14

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$

Table 6 presents the comparative analysis using mean, standard deviation, and analysis of variance, to verify the significance of differences in the Conscious State Expansion (CSE) dimension of Spiritual Intelligence. A significant difference was found between the religious groups, Hindu and Muslim ($F(1,396) = 4.98, p < .05$), indicating that the Hindu group (Mean = 12.62, $SD = 3.55$) exhibits a higher level of Conscious State Expansion compared to the Muslim group (Mean = 11.88, $SD = 3.13$).

A significant difference was also observed between the gender groups ($F(1,396) = 4.85, p < .05$), with females (Mean = 12.62, $SD = 4.32$) demonstrating greater Conscious State Expansion than males (Mean = 11.88, $SD = 3.48$). However, the two-factor interaction effect (Religion \times Gender) across all four groups was not significant, indicating that the patterns of responses across groups were consistent and did not differ in direction.

Table 7

Predictive Result of Religion, Gender and their Interaction on Spiritual Intelligence

SI	Multiple R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	SE	F value	Sig. F
Religion	0.225	0.051	0.048	14.36	21.19	0.00
Gender	0.100	0.010	0.007	14.66	3.99	0.05
Religion* Gender	0.056	0.003	0.001	14.71	1.23	0.27

Variables	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	p
Intercept	-3.31	1.02	-3.25	0.00
religion	6.61	1.44	4.60	0.00
Intercept	1.46	1.04	1.41	0.16
Gender	-2.93	1.47	-2.00	0.05
Intercept	-0.47	0.85	-0.56	0.58
Religion* Gender	1.89	1.70	1.11	0.27

The model summary in Table 7 indicates that religion has a significant predictive effect on Spiritual Intelligence ($R = 0.225, R^2 = 0.051, \text{Adjusted } R^2 = 0.048, F(1, 397) = 21.19, p < .01$). However, the interaction effect of gender and religion and the main effect of gender were not found to be significant. These regression results demonstrate that religion plays a vital role in influencing Spiritual Intelligence, whereas gender does not have a significant effect in the contemporary context.

Discussion

H01: There will be no significant difference in the level of Spiritual Intelligence (SI) between male and female students.

The comparative details of Spiritual Intelligence and its dimensions across male and female groups are presented in Tables 2-6. A significant difference was found between the gender groups (except for Critical Existential Thinking), indicating that gender plays an important and meaningful role in influencing the level of Spiritual Intelligence. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted based on these results.

H02: There will be no significant difference in the level of Spiritual Intelligence (SI) between Hindu and Muslim students.

A significant difference in Spiritual Intelligence and its dimensions was observed between Hindu and Muslim groups in Tables 26. This suggests that religious affiliation, beliefs, and adherence influence an individual's level of Spiritual Intelligence. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted based on these findings.

H03: The interaction effect of religion and gender on Spiritual Intelligence will not be significant.

Based on the results presented in Tables 2-6, this null hypothesis is

accepted, indicating that interaction effect of religion and gender on Spiritual Intelligence is not significant. The primary reason is that Spiritual Intelligence has a religion-neutral conceptual structure, making it universal and broad, which explains this outcome.

Major Findings of the Study

The major findings obtained from this research study are as follows:

- The Hindu group scored higher than the Muslim group on overall spiritual intelligence as well as on all of its dimensions. This implies that the level of spiritual intelligence among Hindu students is higher compared to Muslim students.
- Female students exhibited a higher level of spiritual intelligence than male students.
- Religious affiliation emerged as a dominant factor influencing spiritual intelligence.
- Gender identity was also found to be an effective factor in influencing the level of spiritual intelligence.
- The combined (interaction) effect of religion and gender was not found to be significant.

Conclusion

From Tables 2 to 7, it is evident that Hindu group of students have obtained higher scores on spiritual intelligence and its dimensions than Muslim group of students. The primary reason for this may be that, within Hinduism, the traditions of meditation, philosophy, the Upanishads, the concept of *Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam*, coexistence, and the flexibility in following religious practices foster broader development of spiritual intelligence among Hindu students. In contrast, the relatively lower level of spiritual intelligence among Muslim group of students may be influenced by the religious

Discipline and the structured nature of Islam, which places greater emphasis on adherence to personal faith practices. The significant effect of religion on all dimensions (Tables 2-7) indicates that the distinct beliefs, worship practices, social values, traditions, and spiritual activities within Hinduism and Islam may be influential factors behind these results. Religious education, traditions, rituals, values, spiritual training, and religion-based moral teachings shape individuals' thoughts, mental development, and spiritual intelligence.

The relatively higher performance of the female group on these dimensions may be attributed to factors such as women's more sensitive personality, empathic behaviour, and moral orientation.

Based on the above results (Table 2-7) and hypothesis testing, religious affiliation emerges as a significant predictor of Spiritual Intelligence, while gender also shows a meaningful effect on spiritual intelligence. The non-significant interaction effect on this scale indicates that the response patterns of males and females across both religious groups are not divergent but generally follow the same direction.

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